

USING MODERN METHODS AND METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH.

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Abstract: Today, innovative pedagogical technologies are considered as the most effective tools in the educational process. They are widely used in world foreign language teaching practice. Not all active learning methods are interactive methods. When we say interactive teaching methods, first of all, the method of learning and mastering the subject among students is based on mutual communication. This article discusses the use of interactive methods in English language classes.

Key words: Language, English, independent language learning, educational technologies, project, interest, activity, interactive methods.

Today, the main focus is on the student, his personality and unique inner world. Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is to choose methods and forms of organization of educational activities students that optimally correspond to the set goal of personal development. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in schools has been raised more and more. It is not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the educational process. The main goal of teaching foreign languages is to form and develop the communicative culture of schoolchildren, to teach them to learn a foreign language in practice.

Today, teaching through interactive games is becoming a tradition in schools. It is known that the lesson is conducted on the basis of various games, which ensures that students demonstrate their capabilities, concentrate, improve their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The basis of the use of game technology is the activity that activates and accelerates the student. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity rely on the fundamental needs of a person to express himself, find a stable place in life, self-control, and realize his potential. Any game should be based on generally accepted educational principles and tactics. Educational games should be based on educational subjects. In the process of games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a regular lesson and works freely. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a method of teaching. Pupils participate in game lessons with interest, strive to win, and the teacher also provides education to the pupil through them. The student believes that he can speak, listen, understand, and write in English while playing games, he is interested.

Interactive methods help increase the effectiveness of English lessons. The main criteria of interactive education: conducting informal discussions, the opportunity to freely describe and express the educational material, the number of lectures is small, but the number of seminars is large, the creation of opportunities for students to take initiative, small group, large group, class team assignment, written work and other methods, which are of special importance in increasing the effectiveness of educational work. Interactive methods: - raising students' interest in learning English; - bringing the work of a teacher in English closer to the real conditions of life; - effective communication methods, i.e. proper formation of teacher-student and mutual communication skills; - raising the process of mastering new theoretical knowledge and practical skills to a new level; - increasing students' responsibility for the educational process. Its effectiveness is higher than traditional methods such as interactive methods of teaching, explanation, instruction and use of tools.

The task of the teacher is to create conditions for practical mastery of the language for each student, to choose such teaching methods that allow each student to demonstrate his activity and creativity. The task of the teacher is to activate the cognitive activity of the student in the process of teaching foreign languages. Modern pedagogical technologies, such as collaborative learning, project methodology, use of new information technologies, Internet resources, help to implement a person-oriented approach in the educational process, individualize and differentiate teaching, taking into account the abilities of children, their level of learning. provides. Forms of working with computer training programs in foreign language classes include: learning vocabulary; practice pronunciation; teaching dialogic and monologic speech; teaching writing; development of grammatical events. The possibilities of using Internet resources are huge. The Global Internet provides conditions for students and teachers located anywhere in the world to get any information they need: regional geographical materials, news in the life of young people, articles from newspapers and magazines, etc.

The meaningful basis of mass computerization is related to the fact that the modern computer is an effective tool for optimizing the conditions of mental work, in general, in any of its forms. The computer has one characteristic that defines its use as a tool for teaching others and as an aid in the acquisition of knowledge, and that is its inanimate nature. The machine can have a "friendly" relationship with the user and sometimes "support" him, but he will never show signs of anger and will not let you feel bored. In this sense, the use of computers is perhaps most useful in individualizing some aspects of teaching. The main goal of learning a foreign language at school is the

formation of communicative competence, all other goals (education, training, development) are implemented in the process of realizing this main goal. Communicative approach includes communication training and the formation of intercultural communication skills, which are the basis of Internet activities. Without communication, the Internet has no meaning - it is an international multinational, intercultural society, whose life is based on the electronic communication of millions of people around the world, talking at the same time - this is the number and size of the participants in it. the biggest conversation on. Attending a foreign language class for him, we create a real communication model.

Summary:

Pedagogical technology is essentially organized with the help of forms, methods and tools, increases the effectiveness of pedagogical activity and determines mutual cooperation between teachers. In addition, it ensures students' acquisition of thorough knowledge of educational subjects. forms independent, free and creative thinking skills in students. At the same time, necessary conditions are created for students to realize their potential. It is also necessary to guarantee the priority of democratic and humanitarian ideas in the pedagogical process.

References:

Kambarova Diloram Yusupovna. (2022). THE ROLE OF SPEAKING ACTIVITIES IN ENGLISH TEACHING. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6320456>

Andreevskaya-Levenst ern JI. C. Methods of teaching French in secondary school: Textbook. - M .: Education, 1973. - 222 p.

Qambarova Dilorom Yusupovna. (2022). ON THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. American Journal Of Philological Sciences, 2(10), 12–17. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajps/Volume02Issue10-03>

Babinskaya P. K., Leontyeva T. P., Andreyasyn I. M., Budko A. F., Chepak I. V. A practical course in the methodology of teaching foreign languages: A textbook - Ed. 5th. — M.: Tetra System, 2009. — 288 p.

Bim I. L. Methods of teaching foreign languages as a science and theory of a school textbook. - M .: Russian language, 1977. - 288 p ..

Vereshchagina I. N., Rogova G. V., Yazykova N. V. Methods of teaching English: grades 1-4: A manual for teachers and students of pedagogical universities. - 4th ed. - M .: Education, 2008. - 223 p.

Dzhalalov D. D. Problems of the content of teaching a foreign language. - T .: Fan, 1987. - 110 p.

